

MODERN METHODS OF TREATMENT OF RETINOPATHY OF PREMATURE INFANTS

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Abstract: Preliminary selection of newborns in the risk group for ROP was carried out by a neonatologist. The first ophthalmological examination of newborns in the risk group was carried out at 31-32 weeks of postconceptual age (at 3-4 weeks of life). During the examination, the ophthalmologist was assisted by a pediatric nurse or a neonatologist. In case of an increase in vascular activity and the transition of the process to the 3rd stage, repeated examinations by the same ophthalmologist are very important, which will help to avoid individual errors and correctly determine the medical tactics. In the absence of signs of ROP, newborns were examined every 2 weeks until the completion of retinal vascularization (i.e. until 40-42 weeks of postconceptual age). In the presence of signs of ROP, the examination was carried out once a week. In the case of posterior aggressive ROP, the interval between examinations was 2-3 days. Upon reaching the threshold stage of the process development (stage 3 + in zone I or II), in the presence of posterior aggressive ROP, surgical treatment (laser or cryocoagulation of avascular zones of the retina) was carried out no later than 24-72 hours from the moment of diagnosis. Drug therapy, further treatment tactics and rehabilitation, as well as the scope and methods of treatment of children with ROP in stages 4 and 5 were determined by a consultation involving an ophthalmologist, a neonatologist and the head of the department.

Key words: retinopathy of prematurity, laser coagulation of the retina, oxygen therapy, angioprotectors, posterior aggressive retinopathy of prematurity.

Introduction. The problem of retinopathy of prematurity (ROP) is the most dynamically developing branch of pediatric ophthalmology. In recent years, interest in this problem has increased significantly not only on the part of ophthalmologists, but also on the part of government agencies, which is due to the undoubted social significance of the disease. Improvement of neonatal care in developed countries has led to a progressive decrease in the mortality rate of premature infants with extremely low birth weight. However, it is these children who are at risk of blindness due to ROP due to fibrovascular proliferation during the development of the immature retina. Not all premature infants develop ROP. In 78% of premature infants, ROP regresses in the early stages without treatment, but those infants in whom ROP progresses must be treated. The incidence of ROP varies in different countries, reaching 24.7 per 100,000 live births, and is closely related to the proportion of surviving premature infants, the degree of their somatic burden, immaturity, and nursing conditions [1]. There is a close correlation between the incidence of the disease and the degree of immaturity of the child, which depends on birth weight and gestational age. The more immature the child is born, the higher the probability of developing ROP. The incidence of ROP, according to the literature, varies [2, 3]. For example, V. Seiberth reports that the incidence of ROP depending on birth weight is: up to 1000 g - 67%, 1000-1200 g - 35%, 1250-1500 g - 19%, 1500-2000 g - 10%, and with

a weight of 2000-2500 g - 1% [4]. According to modern concepts, ROP is a severe vitreoretinal eye disease (vasoproliferative retinopathy) that develops in extremely premature infants. The disease was first described in 1942 by T. Terry, a pathologist and ophthalmologist from Texas, as a separate nosological entity. He defined the disease as retrolental fibroplasia, manifested by vascularized fibrous membranes behind the transparent lens, leading to bilateral blindness in premature infants. The term ROP itself, which more accurately reflects the essence of pathological changes developing in the retina of premature infants, was proposed by P. Heath in 1951 [5]. In economically developed countries, a second epidemic of ROP is currently observed, while in developing countries, the wave of ROP is just beginning. Despite many years of intensive clinical and experimental research, the pathogenesis of ROP remains unstudied. It is generally accepted that the disease is based on a disruption of normal retinal vasculogenesis as a result of the action of many different factors. There are many hypotheses for the development of ROP. Most authors believe that the main factor in the development of ROP is the morphological and functional immaturity of the child, the immaturity of the vascular system of the retina, which completes its development in an unfavorable environment. Most authors attribute the leading role in the development of ROP to a combination of retinal immaturity with hyperoxemia. The classical theory of A. Patz and V. Ashton divides the pathogenesis of ROP into 2 phases: vasoobliteration and vasoproliferation [6]. An increase in the partial oxygen tension in the blood during long-term oxygen therapy leads to vasoconstriction, vasoobliteration, and destruction of growing capillaries of the immature retina. As the partial oxygen tension in the blood decreases (under conditions of relative hypoxia), a vascular endothelial proliferation and growth of newly formed vessels. Vasoproliferation develops in response to the release of an angiogenic factor by the retina exposed to hypoxia. The spread of newly formed vessels into the vitreous body contributes to the development of fibrosis with subsequent vitreoretinal tractions. F. Kretzer and H. Hittner [6] describe the theory of ROP induction, according to which retinal blood vessels are formed under normal conditions by canalization of spindle-shaped cells after migration of mesenchymal aprons into the immature retina. Migration, canalization, and endothelial differentiation of spindle-shaped cells occur in the hypoxic environment of the uterus. Premature infants are born with a peripheral zone of avascular retina, which is loaded with a large number of spindle-shaped cells. In response to the action of increased oxygen tension in the blood, mesenchymal spindle-shaped cells form intercellular connections with a gap, which become a barrier to cell migration into the retina, and the normal vascularization process stops. Free radicals formed as a result of increased tissue oxygenation damage spindle-shaped cells, which produce an angiogenic factor that stimulates pathological vascularization of the vitreous body. In premature infants, compared with full-term infants, a deficiency of protective antioxidants (for example, tocopherol) and a decrease in the activity of the main antioxidant enzyme superoxide dismutase are determined. This is why ROP is classified as a free-radical disease [6, 7]. Summarizing the literature data and his own experience, M.E. Prost [6] characterizes the pathogenesis of ROP. In his opinion, in premature infants, as a result of a sudden increase in the oxygen content in the inner layers of the retina, vasoobliteration and damage to immature intraretinal vessels occur, which disrupts the process of normal vascularization of the peripheral parts of the retina. The development of retinal neurons continues, the metabolic activity of the avascular peripheral retina increases. After returning to normal oxygen content (room air), this part of the retina becomes hypoxic. In most cases, spontaneous regression is observed, and the process of normal vascularization of the retina is restored. In some infants, the suppression of retinal vessel development is irreversible. Excessive production of angiogenic factor stimulates fibrovascular proliferation in the vitreous body from parts of the retina adjacent to areas of damaged immature retinal vascularization. Subsequent contraction of the fibrous and glial components of this proliferation leads to the development of retinal detachment. The most convincing hypothesis explains the pathogenesis of ROP by the negative effect of wide fluctuations in oxygen saturation [8]. A sudden change in the partial oxygen tension inside the retina from mild hypoxia to mild hyperoxia results in damage to immature retinal vessels and disrupts the process of normal vascularization of the retinal periphery. The extraordinary sensitivity of vessels to oxygen is characteristic only of the retina

with incomplete vascularization, while the fully vascularized retina is resistant to oxygen damage. The formation of retinal capillaries is especially active at 6–7 months of fetal development, therefore premature babies of this gestation period are especially predisposed to ROP. The pathogenetic role of autoimmune reactions in children with ROP has been studied. It has been established that immune reactions induced by the S-antigen of the retina are one of the factors in the pathogenesis of ROP. In the development of ROP, as well as in children with severe cicatricial stages of ROP, a marked increase in the titer of antibodies to the S-antigen was found [9]. Thus, ROP is a disease in the implementation of the pathogenesis of which many factors participate, and the fluctuation in partial oxygen tension is only one of them. There is a close relationship between the risk of developing and progressing ROP with the degree of immaturity of the child at birth. Generally recognized risk factors are low body weight and small gestational age of the child at birth. The lower the body weight and gestational age, the higher the incidence of ROP. In extremely premature children with a birth weight of less than 750 g, the risk of developing ROP exceeds 90% [7]. The lower the body weight, the more significant the causes of miscarriage: this is not only immaturity, but also a violation of intrauterine development [10]. The development of pathological changes in the retinal vascular system with subsequent vasoproliferation may be due to adverse effects of the mother's body on the fetus and the visual organ during intrauterine development. Among the antenatal factors, gestosis during pregnancy, premature placental abruption and bleeding during childbirth are important; conditions leading to disruption of the uteroplacental and fetal circulation [10]. In the group of children with ROP, there was a tendency for a higher frequency of development of such conditions in mothers as chronic inflammatory gynecological diseases, cesarean section. More often, children with ROP are born from the 4th and subsequent pregnancies. In the group of children with ROP, such diseases as respiratory distress syndrome and severe infectious and inflammatory diseases (pneumonia, meningitis, sepsis) were significantly more often observed. Also in this group, the total duration of oxygen therapy and artificial ventilation of the lungs was significantly longer, with artificial ventilation more often using 80-100% oxygen for more than 3 days. The closest relationship was noted with a duration of oxygen therapy of more than 30 days [10, 11]. As for direct indicators of blood gases, i.e. the presence of periods of hyperoxemia (PaO_2 over 80 mmHg), hypoxemia (PaO_2 less than 40 mmHg), hyper or hypocapnia, reliable differences were revealed only in the frequency of significant fluctuations in blood gas parameters in the neonatal period [10, 11]. Other risk factors for ROP are the standard of infant care, respiratory distress syndrome, recurrent apnea, periventricular leukomalacia, the presence of an open arterial duct, repeated blood transfusions, sepsis, surfactant treatment, multiple pregnancy; the effect of bright light, necrotizing enterocolitis, vitamin E deficiency [12]. A relationship has been established between ambient temperature and the prescription of antibiotics and the incidence of ROP [13]. ROP is a complex eye disease in a sick child's body. Pathological changes affect not only the retina and vitreous body, but also other parts of the visual analyzer in patients with neurological and somatic diseases. ROP is a complex disease that requires a thorough description to facilitate understanding of its development and timely treatment.

The purpose of the work. To evaluate modern methods of treating retinopathy of prematurity.

Materials and methods.

Preliminary selection of newborns in the risk group for ROP was carried out by a neonatologist. The first ophthalmological examination of newborns in the risk group was carried out at 31-32 weeks of postconceptual age (at 3-4 weeks of life). During the examination, the ophthalmologist was assisted by a pediatric nurse or a neonatologist. In case of increasing vascular activity and transition of the process to the 3rd stage, repeated examinations by the same ophthalmologist are very important, which will help to avoid individual errors and correctly determine the medical tactics. In the absence of signs of ROP, newborns were examined every 2 weeks until the completion of retinal vascularization (i.e. until 40-42 weeks of postconceptual age). In the presence of signs of ROP, the examination was carried out once a week. In the

case of posterior aggressive ROP, the interval between examinations was 2-3 days. When the threshold stage of the process development is reached (stage 3 + in zone I or II), in the presence of posterior aggressive ROP, surgical treatment (laser or cryocoagulation of avascular zones of the retina) should be carried out no later than 24-72 hours from the moment of diagnosis. It is desirable that the treatment be carried out at the facility where the child is being nursed. Drug therapy, further treatment tactics and rehabilitation, as well as the scope and methods of treatment of children with ROP in stages 4 and 5 are determined by a council with the participation of an ophthalmologist, a neonatologist and the head of the department. If necessary and in the presence of appropriate medical conditions, the child is transferred to a specialized ophthalmological hospital [16]. Treatment

Medicinal

Angioprotectors: 12.5% ethamsylate solution — 0.3–0.4 ml intramuscularly, intravenously (for newborns weighing less than 1.5 kg); 0.5 ml (for newborns weighing more than 1.5 kg) once a day, daily, for 7–10 days. If necessary (retinal vascular spasm, retinal hemorrhages) — repeated courses of injections at intervals of 10–14 days. Antioxidants: instillations of 1% methylethylpyridinol solution — 1 drop 3–6 times a day, 1% methylethylpyridinol solution parabolbarly — 0.3 ml intramuscularly, 1 ml for 7–10 days. When stage 1 is reached, glucocorticoid instillations are added into the conjunctival cavity: 0.1% dexamethasone solution — 1 drop 4–6 times a day, fluorometholone — 1 drop 6 times a day. At stage 2 of the disease, parabolbar glucocorticoid injections are prescribed: dexamethasone — 0.2 ml every other day until exudation decreases. Forced instillation of glucocorticoids (dexamethasone, fluorometholone) and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (0.1% diclofenac solution) is used — 1 drop 6 times over 1 hour 1 time per day.

Surgical. When the threshold stage was reached (stage 3+ in zone I or II) or in the pre-threshold stage no later than 72 hours after diagnosis, surgical treatment was performed to limit the avascular zone of the retina, which stimulates neovascularization, and to prevent further development and spread of the disease. Retinal coagulation: laser erythrocyte sedimentation rate and cryocoagulation. Indications for retinal laser coagulation were the threshold stage, posterior aggressive ROP and subthreshold stages. Laser coagulation was used with a transscleral and transpupillary approach, most often performed at 35 weeks of gestational age (from 31 to 45 weeks). The operation was performed under general anesthesia and control of a binocular ophthalmoscope using diode ophthalmocoagulators. The effectiveness of photocoagulation was 80-90%. If retinal coagulation was ineffective in the 3rd stage of the active period, extrascleral operations were performed in children's ophthalmology departments of regional hospitals. In the 4th stage of the active period, surgical treatment is performed:

Results and discussion.

Children with ROP require lifelong active observation by an ophthalmologist. The children were observed in ophthalmology offices of polyclinics, consulting offices of regional hospitals and children's vision protection offices [18]. An ophthalmologist of a children's polyclinic conducts an initial examination of premature infants at the age of 1.5 months, and then, if symptoms of the disease are present, every 2 weeks until complete regression of the active phase. In the active phase of the disease, after cryo- or laser coagulation, the child was examined at least once every 2 weeks (preferably, this should be done by the operating ophthalmologist). If necessary, a repeat operation was possible to stabilize the pathological process. Most children with early stages of ROP experienced spontaneous regression or regression following laser or cryocoagulation of the retina. In more severe cases, atrophic areas or residual fibrous tissue were formed on the periphery of the retina, as well as a temporally elongated optic disc, ectopia macula, folds, retinal detachment, partial or total fibroplasia. Some children who had regression of ROP suffered from complications that appeared later in life. These included strabismus, amblyopia, refractive errors, glaucoma, nystagmus, cataracts, corneal dystrophy, microphthalmos, retinal detachment [17].

Conclusions

In recent years, significant progress has been made in understanding the etiology and pathogenesis of ROP, and the relevance of this problem is constantly growing. The outcome of the disease depends on the correctness, coordination and speed of actions of ophthalmologists and neonatologists, the organization and comprehensive screening, as well as the possibility of providing specialized care.

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